

RESEARCH ON POLYETHERSULFONE AND ITS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Polyethersulfone resin has excellent heat resistance, toughness and dielectricity. It is one of the most interesting resins that are investigated and developed in situ. This paper reported Imide Ether (IE) used to modify polyethersulfone (PES) 100P and the resulted resin was indicated by improved heat resistance and strength. The modified PES 100P has been used to blend with PES 200P, and it makes the flexure strength of glass fiber reinforced plastics increased 12%, as well as its thermal performance was not decreased.

INTRODUCTION

A new kind of heat resistance composite matrix, thermoplastics, is keen on by material researchers recently. Compared with thermosetting resins, thermoplastics has high fracture elongation and long shelf life of its prepreg. Polyethersulfone (PES) is one that exhibits good electric properties and has been used in aeronautic and astronautic vehicles(1, 2).

At present, PES 100P and PES 200P can be applicable to composites. However, the \bar{M}_n of PES 100P is not high enough ($\bar{M}_n=13,300$) and strength is low. Reversely, the \bar{M}_n of PES 200P is high ($\bar{M}_n=30,000$), this makes it poor flow performance, unsatisfactory processing property and low composite strength. Owing to the reactive terminal hydroxide groups of PES 100P, it is possible to modify by heat stable Imide Ether (IE) monomer with terminal hydroxide group for improving strength and heat resistance. To realize this purpose, PES 100P and IE were formed salts by strong alkali, then condensation polymerization was carried out between two salts with DDS (diaminodiphenyl sulfone). At last, the residual terminal hydroxide groups were eliminated by methyl chloride. The successful result was shown by infrared spectrum (IR), DSC, TBA analysis. The modified resin was incorporated into PES 200 for improving the flow performance and adhesive strength. The GFRP composite of this matrix keeps the same heat resistance of PES 200P and its flexure strength is increased 12%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

SYNTHESIS OF IMIDE ETHER

Molecular reaction eq. of the synthesis of IE was shown as follows (5).

CHARACTERIZATION OF RESIN

MODIFICATION OF PES 100P

Salt Formation Reaction both IE and PES 100P could react with alkali (i. e. KOH) by dehydration and formed salt.

Expanding Chain and Closed Terminal Reaction Using DCDPS (4, 4'-Dichlorodiphenylsulfone). The expanding chain reaction was complex.

Physical and Mechanical Characterization of Modified PES 100P Resins Table 1 shown that

the Tg and viscosity of EXP 31 and EXP 32 were higher than that of PES 100P. The mixture of PES 200P with EXP 31 or EXP 32 had the same Tg as PES 200P, but low viscosity.

Table 1: Comparison of Tg of Different Resins

No	Resin system	Viscosity (m/s ²)x10 ⁶	Tg, °C	
			DSC	TBA
1	PES 100P	99.47	224	264
2	PES 200P	203.26	228	268
3	200P,85%,100P,15%	155.90	226	265
5	200P,90%,100P,20%	147.28	224	264
12	200P,90%,EXP 28,10%	—	220	260
13	200P,90%,EXP 32,10%	187.23	232	268
14	200P,90%,EXP 31,10%	164.45	227	267

The film tensile strength of PES 100P, PES 200P and modified resin systems were listed in Table 2. It shown that the modification of PES 100P was realized.

Table 2: Film Tensile Strength of Different Resin Systems

Resin system	Film tensile strength (MPa)
PES 200P	39.93
PES 100P	27.27
200P,80%,100P,20%	35.55
200P,95%,100P,5%	38.19
200P,90%,100P,10%	36.94
200P,90%,EXP 31,10%	37.94
200P,90%,EXP 32,10%	38.09

Mechanical Properties of GFRP Composites

The flow performance and adhesive property of PES 200P were improved by blending PES 200P with EXP 31 or EXP 32 which had lower viscosity.

Table 3: Comparison the Mechanical Properties of GFRP Composites with unmodified and modified Resin Systems

Resin system	200P	200P+100P	200P+EXP 31	200P+EXP 32
Flexural strength (Weft) (MPa)	268.0	249.4	278.3	301.2
Resin content,%	49.6	50.1	48.2	51.38
Molding parameters	310°C, 1.37 MPa, 1.5 h			

Table 3 shown that the flexural strength of composites raised 12% with the resin system blended of EXP 32.

CONCLUSIONS

1. The results of IR, DSC and TBA analyses had demonstrated that EXP 31 and EXP 32 were obtained by modification PES 100P with Imider Ether. The product thus modified behaved

better mechanical property and process performance. Further studies on the structure and mechanism of the reaction shall be continued.

2. It can conclude that the GFRP Composite using the mixture of EXP 31 or EXP 32 with PES 200P as matrix system kept its heat resistance and improved flexural strength at ambient condition increased 12% than that of PES 200P alone.

3. The modified resin (EXP 31 or EXP 32) was suitable used as composite matrix. However, optimization of composite processing parameters and composite performance may be further studied.

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